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TRACES OF THE COMMON ORIGIN OF *CARTE PISANE*, *CORTONA CHART* AND PIETRO VESCONTE'S CHARTS

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ABSTRACT

Anonymous Carte Pisane (c. 1275) and Cortona chart (c. 1300), as well as Pietro Vesconte's charts made in 1311 and 1313, which represent some of the earliest known portolan charts, were cartometrically analysed in order to examine the geometric similarities between their coastal renderings. The research results show that not only the majority of their territorial coverage was drawn very similarly to each other, but also that there are certain parts of the coastline that are nearly identical between all the examined charts. Also, the magnitude and orientation of displacement vectors of residuals revealed that the Mediterranean and Black Sea areas on charts contains seven subsections which are on average, as twice as accurate in comparison to the same area treated as a whole. The fundamental conclusion is that there is a high probability that the coastline renderings on the earliest known portolan charts are actually more or less skilfully made copies of the same source material used as a graphic template. The hypothetical source might have been an atlas whose origins date back to before the Middle Ages, containing charts whose extents were, perhaps, similar to the extents of detected subsections, which medieval cartographers were not able to assemble correctly due to their ignorance of map projections.

KEYWORDS: early portolan charts, cartometric analysis, Carte Pisane, Cortona chart, Pietro Vesconte

1. INTRODUCTION

The immense accuracy of coastline renderings on portolan charts, which, as far as is known, suddenly appeared in mid- to late-thirteenth century, was never fully and objectively explained, and still, after approximately a century and a half of abundant scientific effort, their origin remains a mystery. In his 1904 article in *Nature*, for example, Sir Charles R. Beazley described them as *the first true maps* (Beazley 1904: 159-161), while Edward L. Stevenson considered them *the first modern scientific maps* (Stevenson 1911: 2). The earliest portolan chart known to exist is the anonymous work, commonly known as *Carte Pisane* (Figure 1), assumed to be made in mid- to late-thirteenth century. The attribute *Pisane* was given to it because it was owned by a family from Pisa from whom French cartographer Edme-François Jomard purchased it and brought it to the French *Royal Library* in 1839, although the chart itself was probably made in Genoa (Berthelot 1839: 360; Crone 1953: 30). Another anonymous early-made portolan chart is the so-called *Cortona chart* (Figure 1) named after *Biblioteca dell'Accademia Etrusca di Cortona* where it is archived, and which could, perhaps, be of even older date than *Carte Pisane*, according to Vera Armignacco (Armignacco 1957) and Giuseppe Caraci (Caraci, 1959), who Tony Campbell refers to in his *Portolan Charts from the Late Thirteenth Century to 1500* book chapter (Campbell 1987: 402, note 243).¹ One argument for its hypothetical precedence of *Carte Pisane* is the absence of Manfredonia which was founded in 1258 by Manfred, the king of Sicily, and which was labelled on *Carte Pisane*. Namely, on the *Carte Pisane*, Manfredonia was written in black, while the neighbouring Siponto, which had a more important role before Manfredonia was established, was written in red (used for highlighting the locations of greater importance).

¹ Additional information about the general characteristics of portolan charts can be found in Campbell's extensive and detailed book chapter which can be downloaded for free at the following link: https://press.uchicago.edu/books/HOC/HOC_V1/Volume1.html

For this reason, it is assumed that the chart was created during the construction and expansion of Manfredonia, where the population of Siponto was gradually transferred (Campbell 1987: 426). Another argument according to which the *Cortona chart* might have been made earlier than *Carte Pisane* are the inscriptions on its back side that refer to Palestine and share similarities with the crusade proposals discussed at the Council of Lyons in 1274 (Campbell 1987: 402, note 243).

Figure 1. Anonymous *Carte Pisane* and *Cortona chart*, georeferenced on a modern map. Charts sources: *Bibliothèque nationale de France*, GE B-1118 (RES); *Biblioteca dell'Accademia Etrusca di Cortona*, Port.105. Basemap shapefile source: *marineregions.org* (Claus et al., 2017).

Late medieval Italy is considered to be the birthplace of the number of early-made preserved portolan charts. Pietro Vesconte, whose origins were Genoese, created the earliest known portolan chart whose author and the year of production – *Petrus Vesconte de Janua fecit ista carta ann[o] dni MCCCXI* – were noted

explicitly on its carrier material (Nordenskiöld 1897: 57). However, his 1311 chart (Figure 2), and all the others made by him² until 1327 were, actually, made in Venice and visually seem to represent an evolutionary step forward in comparison to *Carte Pisane* and *Cortona chart*, especially because the Atlantic coastline appears to have been drawn significantly more accurate in Vesconte's 1313 atlas (Figure 2) (Campbell 1987: 407, 432, 434, 460).

Figure 2. Pietro Vesconte's portolan chart (1311) and the composite of it and the western sheet from his 1313 atlas. Chart sources: *Archivio di Stato di Firenze*, CN 01; *Bibliothèque nationale de France*, CPL GE DD-687 (RES). Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus et al., 2017).

² The author of charts made in 1321 and 1327 is Perrinus (Perrino) Vesconte. Adolf E Nordenskiöld believed Perrinus is a variation of the name Petrus (Nordenskiöld 1987: 58), while Paolo Revelli believed Perrinus was Petrus Vesconte's son or a nephew (Revelli 1937, according to Campbell 1987: 407, note 274).

2. SCOPE AND METHODOLOGY

The fundamental research aim was to look for geometric similarities between the coastal renderings of the areas found on *Carte Pisane*, *Cortona chart*, and Pietro Vesconte’s 1311 chart, and on the western sheet of his 1313 atlas (Table 1) with the application of cartometric approach, and to examine which are the exact differences between Vesconte’s creations and their predecessors, commonly considered to be less-sophisticated. Besides being some of the earliest portolan charts known to exist, the main criterion for the selection of the chart sample is the appearance of their scale-bars, which were designed in a circular fashion, unlike the later iterations of portolan charts on which scale-bars are, uniformly, linear in design (Campbell 1978: 395). The only other known chart made at an apparently less-sophisticated level is the so-called *Avignon chart* (Mille 2021), but its remaining fragment is badly deteriorated in comparison to its supposed original extent and was therefore unsuitable for the research.³

Table 1. Information regarding the chart sample.

CHART DESCRIPTION:	SIZE [mm]:	APPROX. MAP SCALE:	TERRITORIAL COVERAGE:	CONTROL POINTS:
Anonymous Carte Pisane ; considered as the earliest known portolan chart, made in mid- to late-thirteenth century, property of: <i>Bibliothèque nationale de France, département Cartes et plans</i> , call no.: GE B-1118 (RES)	1063×519	1:4,800,000	Atlantic Ocean (partially), Mediterranean Sea, part of the Black Sea (the majority of which is now damaged beyond recognition)	339
Anonymous Cortona chart ; one of the earliest known portolan charts, made in late thirteenth or early fourteenth century, property of: <i>Biblioteca dell'Accademia Etrusca di Cortona</i> , call no.: Port.105	594×475	1:6,250,000	Atlantic Ocean (partially), Central and East Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea (with Sea of Marmara and Sea of Azov)	293
Pietro Vesconte's chart (1311) , the earliest known signed and dated portolan chart, property of: <i>Archivio di Stato di Firenze</i> , call no.: CN 01	632×483	1:5,400,000	Central and East Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea (with Sea of Marmara and Sea of Azov)	296
The western sheet of Pietro Vesconte's atlas (1313) , the earliest known portolan atlas, property of: <i>Bibliothèque nationale de France, département Cartes et plans</i> , call no.: CPL GE DD-687 (RES)	480×412	N Atl.: 1:7,200,000 S Atl. & W Med.: 1:5,570,000	Atlantic coast of West Europe and Northwest Africa and West Mediterranean Sea	177 (N. Atl.: 74, S Atl. & W Med.: 103)

The quantitative analysis of old maps and charts was initially introduced in the late nineteenth century by Hermann Wagner, who coined the term *cartometric*, and advocated its application for future generations of researchers because the existing approach to the study of old maps at the time was limited to subjective visual observations. He also pioneered the idea that portolan charts are, most likely, composites made of sub-charts pieced together (Wagner 1896 (1969): 478, 483). In his 1987 doctoral thesis, Scott A. Loomer cartometrically analysed 26 portolan charts, the majority of which were made in the fifteenth century. He concluded that their geometry is most similar to the geometry of a modern map in Mercator projection, that individual basins show variations in their geometric properties, and that all the charts he examined were most probably copied using one or more prototypes as templates (Loomer 1987: 166-173). In a more recent study, Roel Nicolai cartometrically analysed five portolan charts and concluded that they were most likely created by joining together different sub-charts. He also found similarities between the geometry of portolan charts and that of a modern map in Mercator projection, which does not correspond to the late medieval level of science and technology, to which he provided an extensive and detailed argumentation supported by the historical data (Nicolai 2014: 169-270, 401-410). In 2018, Evangelos Livieratos and Chrysoula Boutoura

³ The other two early-made charts are the so-called *Lucca chart* (*Archivio di Stato di Lucca*, Fondo Stampe n. 1193), and the chart made by Giovanni di Carignano (*Archivio di Stato di Firenze*, CN 02). *Lucca chart* is believed to have been made before 1327, its map scale is drawn in a linear fashion, and it does not appear to be less sophisticated aesthetics-wise. Carignano’s chart, presumably made in the early thirteenth century, was destroyed in 1943 (the only remaining artefact is its monochromatic photo-reproduction), but it appears to be less accurate, and not a typical portolan chart (Campbell 1987: 438).

published a paper about the cartometric analysis of *Carte Pisane* (as a whole), which they compared to a modern map in Mercator projection. They concluded that the locations of its highest accuracy correspond to the areas in which the most prominent naval forces of the Mediterranean during the late medieval period (Byzantine, Arab, Latin, and Norman) were active (Livieratos, Boutoura 2018: 166).

Figure 3. The flowchart of cartometric analysis.

The selected charts were georeferenced on a modern map in Mercator projection⁴ with the application of 4-parameter Helmert similarity transformation to preserve the shape of their coastlines in relative terms (Modenov, Parkhomenko 1965: 77–93),⁵ and each chart was georeferenced in three different scenarios in order to suffice the particular research demands. The first scenario (Figure 1, Figure 2) was performed by using the complete number of control (*identical*) points identified on each chart (Table 1) to obtain their individual metrics (longitudinal and latitudinal *RMSE* accuracy, map scale, and tilt) across their entire territorial coverage, except for the North Atlantic coast on the composite of Vesconte’s two charts. The second scenario, shown in the chapter 3. *Shared Geometric Similarities between the Charts*, and whose criteria are explained in more depth in the following paragraphs, was performed using a reduced number of control points – those which are located within their *intersect areas* (Figure 5, Figure 6) in order to maximize the reliability of their inter-comparison. In the third scenario, shown in the chapter 4. *The Subsectional Geometry of Charts*, each chart was divided into subsections (Figure 8, Figure 9, Figure 10) whose approximate boundaries were determined according to the magnitude and orientation of displacement vector residuals when charts are treated as a whole (Figure 4). The accuracy of charts and their subsections was expressed as *RMSE dLON* and *RMSE dLAT* [km] (Figure 3), by respecting the four *degrees of freedom* allowed by the Helmert transformation.⁶

⁴ It was selected as a plane of reference because the previous extensive and detailed research (Loomer 1987; Nicolai 2014) suggests that portolan charts were, most likely, made in a normal conformal cylindrical projection.

⁵ Helmert transformation was also applied by Loomer (Loomer 1978: 113-114), while Nicolai, as well as Livieratos and Boutoura applied 6-parameter affine transformation, which allows each of the chart’s axes (*X* and *Y*) to be scaled and rotated individually—in order to obtain the best-fit (Nicolai 2014: 455-458; Livieratos, Boutoura 2018: 163).

⁶ Since there are $n-2$ statistically significant points per axis in the *LSE* (*least squares adjustment*) with the application of Helmert transformation, the cumulative number of statistically significant points for computing charts’ estimated accuracy (*RMSE dLON* and *RMSE dLAT*) is $2n-4$ (Jenny, Hurmi 2011: 403–405; Penzkofer 2016: 27–28).

Figure 4. The magnitude and orientation of displacement vectors of residuals on selected charts. Basemap shapefile source: marinerregions.org (Claus et al., 2017).

3. SHARED GEOMETRIC SIMILARITIES BETWEEN THE CHARTS

When the Mediterranean and Black Sea area on each chart georeferenced as a whole is observed individually and compared to the rest without a proper overlap of their coastlines (Figure 1, Figure 2) it might appear that they do not share many common geometrical characteristics. Simply put; to the naked eye, their mapping errors seem to follow individual patterns, which vary among charts. For example, the positioning of Corsica and Sardinia, and the shape of the entire Aegean Sea, appears to be more accurate on *Carte Pisane* in comparison to the *Cortona chart*. Also, the whole West and Central Mediterranean area seems to be drawn more accurately on Vesconte's charts in comparison to both the *Carte Pisane* and *Cortona chart*. However, charts' accuracy values (when charts are treated as a whole) do not show significant variations within the sample. The accuracy of Vesconte's composite, for example, is 29.8 kms, which is a slightly poorer result than that of *Carte Pisane* with an accuracy of 28.4 kms, while the accuracy of *Cortona chart* is 33.0 kms, but its latitudinal accuracy is significantly greater in comparison to Vesconte's composite (Table 2).

In order to determine more objectively whether there is a certain number of geometrical features that are shared between two or more charts or not, they should be georeferenced according to certain criteria, whose purpose is to derive their optimal *intersection area* across which their cartometric inter-comparison can be performed with greater reliability (solid vectorized coastlines in Figure 5 and Figure 6). First, the areas that appear significantly inaccurate to the naked eye (like the Atlantic coast on *Carte Pisane* and *Cortona chart*) should be excluded. Second, because the territorial coverage on charts is not equal, the control points across the areas that do not exist on a chart of a poorer territorial extent should be excluded when the chart of a greater territorial extent (on which those areas are shown) is being georeferenced. For example, the West Mediterranean area, shown on *Carte Pisane* in its entirety, is missing on the *Cortona chart* and Vesconte's 1311 chart. It seems to be that it was originally drawn on the *Cortona chart* before its forced removal (whenever had it occurred in history), while Pietro Vesconte intentionally selected the Côte d'Azur in the north and present-day west Tunisian coast in the south to be the western limits of his 1311 chart. Also, the vast majority of the Black Sea area (together with the Sea of Marmara and the Sea of Azov) on *Carte Pisane* deteriorated beyond recognition even before Jomard obtained it in the mid-nineteenth century and used it to create his facsimile.⁷ The third criterion was the exclusion of the control points across the Adriatic Sea on all charts, because on *Carte Pisane* its coastline shows a significant rotational offset in comparison to the orientation of the remaining coastline areas,⁸ which could affect the georeferencing process and make it less comparable to other charts.

Georeferencing of *Carte Pisane* and Vesconte's composite across their *intersection area* reveals the existence of significant variations between the two on a regional basis. For example, the coasts of present-day southeast Spain and south France seem to have been drawn more accurately by Vesconte, as well as the whole Adriatic Sea basin, but the positioning of Corsica, Sardinia, Sicily, and the whole Ligurian and Tyrrhenian coast seems to be more accurate on *Carte Pisane*, as well as the rendering of the entire East Mediterranean and the Aegean Sea (Figure 5).

⁷ A high-quality digital reproduction of Jomard's *Carte Pisane* facsimile can be downloaded for free at the following link: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Carte_Pisane_Jomard.png

⁸ The relative rotational offset of the Adriatic Sea on *Carte Pisane* was used by Wagner (among his several other arguments) to support his hypothesis that portolan charts could be composites (Wagner 1896 (1969): 481, 483).

Figure 5. Regional similarities and differences between coastlines on *Carte Pisane* and the composite of Pietro Vesconte's chart (1311) and western atlas sheet (1313), georeferenced across their *intersection area*. Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus et al., 2017).

Although Vesconte's 1311 chart and the western sheet from his 1311 atlas were, according to his beliefs, made in the same map scale (because their scale-bars are of the same size), and were, thus, optimal to join them into a composite which revealed his cartographic perception of the areas usually displayed on later portolan charts, it is still an artificially created map. On the other hand, because the West Mediterranean seems to be drawn more simplified on *Carte Pisane*, and because the preserved territorial extent of the *Cortona chart* is nearly identical to the limits of Vesconte's 1311 chart, it is logical to inter-compare the coastlines on those three charts across the *intersection area* which suits the relatively reduced boundaries of the latter two. The overlap of *Carte Pisane* and *Cortona chart* coastlines (the upper part of Figure 6) reveals that the westernmost parts on both charts are drawn nearly identically, as well as the islands of Crete and Cyprus and the whole northeast corner of the East Mediterranean (the area between Alanya in present-day Türkiye, including the Gulf of Iskenderun – which was not rendered accurately – and Latakia in present-day Syria), which is, appearance-wise, in fact, common to all three charts. On the western front, *Carte Pisane* and Vesconte's 1311 chart seem to share nearly identical renderings of the Ligurian and northern Tyrrhenian coast, and the coasts of Gulf of Taranto, Calabria, and Sicily on the European side, as well as the whole stretch of today's Tunisian coast on the African side (the middle part of Figure 6). Apart from the already mentioned northeast corner of the East Mediterranean, the near-identical coastline renderings on *Cortona chart* and Vesconte's 1311 chart are located on the eastern front and include the southern half of Peloponnesus, the island of Crete, and the southwestern corner of Anatolia in the north, and the coastal strip between the Gulf of Sirte and Tobruk in present-day Libya in the south (the lower part of Figure 6).

Figure 6. Regional similarities and differences between the selected portolan charts, georeferenced across their intersection area. Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus et al., 2017).

4. THE SUBSECTIONAL GEOMETRY OF CHARTS

The comparison of coastline renderings revealed that the islands of Corsica, Sardinia and Sicily, and the whole mainland Ligurian, Tyrrhenian, and Calabrian and Adriatic coasts in the north, as well as present-day Tunisian coast in the south on the *Cortona Chart* are uniformly tilted clockwise in comparison to *Carte Pisane* and Vesconte's 1311 chart. The main reason for this is the 4° clockwise tilt of its western wind rose relative to its eastern counterpart, which did not occur afterwards due to careless treatment of the chart but was a genuine (and vast) plotting-error made directly by the cartographer who drew it (Figure 7) and who, also, plotted it more carelessly (considerably more elliptical and with rhumbs that not meet at its centre) in comparison to the eastern one. Intriguingly, the westernmost coast on the chart (approximately past the Toulon in present-day France in the north and Cap de Fer in present-day Algiers in the south) do not follow that pattern – yet, those areas act as a sort of *inflection points*, west of which coastline contours follow a different direction, which is orientation-wise nearly identical to those on *Carte Pisane* (Figure 6).

Figure 7. The western wind rose (purple dotted line), as well as the geometry of the majority of the western one-third of its preserved extent, on the *Cortona chart* is tilted 4° clockwise compared to its eastern wind rose (magenta dashed line) and the geometry of the surrounding area. Chart source: *Biblioteca dell'Accademia Etrusca di Cortona*, Port.105. Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus et al., 2017).

This phenomenon, with the addition of the orientation-wise variations of the Adriatic and the Black Sea on *Carte Pisane*, as well as Vesconte's plotting of the Adriatic Sea and Gulf of Taranto far westward, completely detached from the Ionian Sea and the rest of the Central Mediterranean in his 1313 atlas, and supported by the previous research results (Wagner 1896; Loomer 1987; Nicolai 2014) initiated a more detailed cartometric approach to the geometry of selected charts. In it, the displacement vectors of residuals (Figure 4) for each chart were observed in detail, and it was noticed that there are, actually, clusters of vectors that share similar magnitude and orientation across the particular sub-area shown on a chart, delimited by *inflection points*, which act as transition-zones between neighbouring clusters. In some cases,

such as the area along the southwest coast of present-day Spain and the south coast of present-day France, for example, these transitions are smooth (labelled as *soft-knee inflection points*), while in other cases, such as the area between Sardinia in the north and Sicily and present-day Tunisian coast in the south, those transitions are considerably rougher (labelled as *sharp-knee inflection points*). It was also noticed that in the area around the city of Algiers, two neighbouring clusters of opposite orientations meet and thus alter the charts' geometry acting as a *compression point*. On the other hand, the Aegean Sea, as well as the Black Sea and the Sea of Azov, appear to be two separate *divergence zones*, meaning that the two areas were mapped in a relatively larger map scale, or, perhaps, in (two) separate relatively larger map scales.

Figure 8. The comparison of coastline on the *Cortona chart* and on Pietro Vesconte's 1311 chart if the Mediterranean and Black Sea areas are treated as a whole (black line) and if charts' coastlines are segmented into cartometrically determined subsections (colour-coded lines). Chart sources: *Biblioteca dell'Accademia Etrusca di Cortona*, Port.105; *Archivio di Stato di Firenze*, CN 01. Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus et al., 2017).

The next step was to georeference each chart again piece-wise in order to obtain a better insight into what appears to be the complex mosaic of chart-subsections, whose boundaries do not seem to follow the typical layout of Mediterranean Sea sub-basins. By starting from a certain location (say, the westernmost point on the chart), control points are successively added until residual vectors that show significantly different characteristics start to emerge – an indicator that the georeferencing process has probably stepped into the area that significantly differs geometry-wise. The cluster of those ‘extreme’ residuals should, then, be removed and georeferencing process completed for that particular piece of the chart. After the first piece (which shows approximately similar magnitudes and directions of residual-vectors across its entire area) is successfully georeferenced, the georeferencing of the next one begins from the area where the ‘extreme’ residuals were detected in the previous session, and so on until the last piece is georeferenced, that is, until the whole chart is georeferenced piece-wise. The end result is, in fact, the multiple georeferencing iterations of the same chart, which differ from each other in the way that on each of them only one subsection of the chart (with its control points) is considered, while the remaining areas of the chart are ignored. The statistical *outliers* (the subset of points whose residuals are relatively high and affect the normal distribution) were not rejected during the subsectional georeferencing of the charts, nor previously when the charts were treated as a whole. The reason for that is that all the control points which are identified on the charts (*identical points*), as well as the shapes of the coastline-contours that connect them, are the ‘imprint’ of the manual (free hand) approach applied by the cartographers of the late Middle Ages who drew them, and were, thus, decided to remain absorbed within charts’ metrics.⁹

With the application of the described approach, a number of coastal subsections ‘emerged’ from selected portolan charts, depending on the spatial extent taken into consideration.¹⁰ The Black Sea and The Sea of Azov appear to be one unit, as well as the whole North Atlantic coast (on Vesconte’s atlas sheet) while the Mediterranean Sea seems to have been composed of six subsections whose exact boundaries slightly differ among charts, and whose contact points are not points *per se*, but smaller areas that function as transition-zones. In general, its westernmost unit, labelled as the *West Mediterranean subsection*, borders the *Upper West Mediterranean subsection* on its northeastern front (near Toulon), and the *Central Mediterranean subsection* on its southeastern front (near the city of Algiers). The *Upper West Mediterranean subsection* covers the Ligurian and Tyrrhenian coasts and the islands of Corsica and Sardinia. The *Central Mediterranean subsection* stretches approximately from the city of Algiers in the west to the cape Ras Amir in present-day Libya in the east, where it meets the *East Mediterranean subsection*. On its northern and northeastern front, it includes the island of Sicily, the Calabrian promontory, as well as the Epirus coast, where it borders the *Adriatic Sea subsection* (which contains the Gulf of Taranto as well) in the north, and the *Aegean Sea subsection* in the east. The easternmost unit is the *East Mediterranean subsection*, which borders the *Aegean Sea subsection* on its northwestern front, near the island of Rhodes (Figure 8, Figure 9). The most prominent exceptions can be found on the *Cortona chart*, where the middle part of the mainland Tyrrhenian coast fits better with the *Adriatic Sea subsection*, while the entire coast of Epirus, Peloponnesus, and the island of Crete fit better with the *East Mediterranean subsection*. On the other two charts, the Epirus coastline and the western front of Peloponnesus fit better with the *Central Mediterranean subsection*, while its eastern front and the island of Crete fit better with the *Aegean Sea subsection*.

⁹ The existence of segments from which the portolan charts were most likely compiled in the late Middle Ages is not new. As stated earlier; Loomer and Nicolai had already done extensive research on the subject, but the methodology applied in all three cases was not the same, and therefore each research yielded different outcomes. Loomer applied Helmert transformation and did not remove the statistical outliers of residuals as well, but he opted for an *a priori* sub-basin division, previously determined by the historian Philippe Braudel (Loomer 1987: 159) and not related to the distribution of residual-vectors. Also, none of the charts examined in this research were analysed by him. Nicolai analysed the *Carte Pisane*, but the boundaries of sub-charts determined by him are the result of 6-parameter affine transformation and the removal of outliers after the repetitive statistical testing of the residuals (Nicolai, 2014: 207-210, 240-243).

¹⁰ The term *subsection* (instead of just a *section* or a *sub-basin*) was coined intentionally because the spatial distribution of cartometrically determined chart-pieces is not deducible with the naked eye, and because their borders seem to be mainly unrelated to the typical Mediterranean sub-basin division (Figure 10).

Figure 9. The comparison of coastline on *Carte Pisane* and on the composite of Pietro Vesconte’s 1311 chart and his 1313 atlas if the Mediterranean and Black Sea areas are treated as a whole (black line) and if charts’ coastlines are segmented into cartometrically determined subsections (colour-coded lines). Chart sources: *Bibliothèque nationale de France*, GE B-1118 (RES); *Archivio di Stato di Firenze*, CN 01; *Bibliothèque nationale de France*, CPL GE DD-687 (RES). Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus et al., 2017).

The estimated accuracy of subsections expressed as longitudinal and latitudinal *root mean-squared error* (RMSE) of geodesic distances [km] on the surface of WGS84 ellipsoid is variable (Table 2). The most accurate parts of every chart are the *Upper West Mediterranean* and *Adriatic Sea* subsections, which are smaller in size. The *Aegean Sea subsection* is also a smaller one, but it was, in general, rendered similarly or even slightly less accurate than the *Central Mediterranean section* whose area is considerably greater, while the least accurate parts are *East Mediterranean* and *Black Sea sections*. The most important result of this analysis is that the average accuracy of subsections is, in general, approximately two times greater than the

accuracy of the Mediterranean and Black Sea areas when treated as a whole – the average of estimated longitudinal accuracies of subsections detected on *Cortona chart*, for example, is as nearly as three times greater than the estimated longitudinal accuracy of the whole chart.

Table 2. The estimated accuracy values of charts and their subsections. The greater of the two axial values (whether *RMSE dLON* or *RMSE dLAT*), which represents the overall accuracy of a chart or its subsection is put in bold.

	Whole Chart*	subsections								Avg. subject. acc. [km]	Avg. accuracy improvement [%]
		North Atlantic	West Med	Upper West Med	Central Med	Adriatic	Aegean	East Med	Black**		
<i>Carte RMSE dLON</i> [km]	28.4	-	17.4	10.9	9.7	7.7	17.4	16.5	-	13.3	213.5%
<i>Pisane RMSE dLAT</i> [km]	25.4	-	14.6	12.3	14.6	10.6	15.8	21.6	-	14.9	170.4%
<i>Cortona RMSE dLON</i> [km]	33.0	-	-	7.9	10.4	11.9	10.2	11.3	17.3	11.5	286.9%
<i>chart RMSE dLAT</i> [km]	23.6	-	-	11.1	13.7	12.4	13.3	14.5	13.6	13.1	180.1%
Vesconte <i>RMSE dLON</i> [km]	21.6	16.2	10.7	8.6	14.9	13.0	14.6	16.4	15.3	13.4	161.2%
composite <i>RMSE dLAT</i> [km]	29.8	19.6	10.2	7.2	11.7	12.3	11.2	17.1	14.9	12.7	234.6%

* Vesconte's composite was georeferenced as a (conditional) whole chart with the exclusion of its north Atlantic coast (dashed black line in the lower part of the Figure 2).

** The *Black Sea subsection* on *Cortona chart* was georeferenced with the exclusion of the Sea of Azov.

Apparently sketchy and less-sophisticated rendering of the Black Sea coastline on the *Cortona chart* (Figure 1), is primarily due to its significant enlargement in map scale. Namely, its *Black Sea subsection* (with the exclusion of the Sea of Azov) was drawn in a map scale which is 13.2% larger in comparison to the map scale of its *Central Mediterranean subsection*. On Vesconte's chart, the rendering of the Black Sea coastline appears more accurate (Figure 2), but its estimated accuracy is not significantly greater in comparison to *Cortona chart* (Table 2) – its apparently greater accuracy on Vesconte's chart is due to its map scale being only 2.9% larger in comparison to the map scale of its *Central Mediterranean subsection* (Table 3). Regarding the map scale variations among the selected charts, the *Carte Pisane* is the one with the lowest cross-dispersion, with a standard deviation of only 2.6%, while the standard deviations on *Cortona chart* and Vesconte's 1311 chart are 6.3% and 6.2%, respectively. The main reason for that is the map scale of the *Aegean Sea subsection* on *Carte Pisane*, whose author tailored it considerably more realistic. On the composite of Vesconte's two charts, the standard deviation of map scales without the *North Atlantic subsection* is 6.1%, or 10.5% if all of its subsections are considered because, in his 1313 atlas, he drew the coasts of the North Atlantic in a significantly smaller map scale (Table 3).

Table 3. The relative map scale of chart-subsections in comparison to the *Central Mediterranean subsection*. Values lower than 100.0% mean that the particular subsection is rendered smaller on a chart and vice versa.

		subsections							
		North Atlantic	West Med	Upper West Med	Central Med	Adriatic	Aegean	East Med	Black
<i>Carte Pisane</i>	relative map scale [%]	-	102.9%	99.9%	100.0%	98.5%	100.4%	94.2%	-
<i>Cortona chart</i>	relative map scale [%]	-	-	103.9%	100.0%	100.8%	116.6%	103.4%	113.2%
Vesconte composite	relative map scale [%]	74.1%	95.8%	95.3%	100.0%	96.6%	114.2%	99.9%	102.9%

The analysis of charts' subsectional-metrics revealed that their individual (clockwise) tilts, induced by the *least squares estimation (LSE)* process with the application of Helmert transformation – that occur because the coastline renderings on portolan charts were drawn as tilted anticlockwise – are variable. The consensus view among the majority of scholars is that the anticlockwise orientation of coastlines was an unintentional by-product that emerged because the eastern orientation of magnetic declination in the late Middle Ages affected the magnetic compass used by the sailors to track the bearings of the ship routes and to accumulate the spatial data upon which the portolan charts were originally created. Those sailors were, presumably, unaware of the existence of magnetic declination,¹¹ and, thus, aligned their charts with the direction of north which they believed to be true. Early scholar protagonists of the idea that the portolan charts were genuine products based on the bearing- and distance-data collected by the sailors of the late Middle Ages were, for example, Konrad Kretschmer (1909), Stevenson (1911) and Eva G. R. Taylor (1951a; 1951b), while Ramon J. Pujades (2007), Joaquim A. Gaspar (2007; 2008) and Peter Mesenburg (2021) represent the more recent generation. The *LSE*-induced tilts of chart subsections (θ_{LSE}) were compared to magnetic declination values for the year 1250 (δ_{1250}), derived from the *CALS3k.4* paleomagnetic model (Korte, Konstable 2011). The year 1250 was selected because of the supposed creation date of *Carte Pisane*, and, perhaps, even *Cortona chart*. The differences between the two ($\Delta\theta_{LSE}$) seem to be very small for its western half of the Mediterranean Sea (the *West*, *Upper West*, and *Central Mediterranean* subsections), while its eastern half (the *Aegean*, *East Mediterranean*, and *Black Sea* subsections) contains offset-values which are considerably greater (Table 4).

Table 4. The *LSE*-induced tilts of charts and their subsections (the upper part), magnetic declination for the year 1250 according to the *CALS3k.4* model, and differences between chart (subsections) tilt and *CALS3k.4* values (the lower part). *CALS3k.4* data source: GEOMAGIA50.v3.2, accesses on March 2023.

		Whole Chart	subsections							
			North Atlantic	West Med	Upper West Med	Central Med	Adriatic	Aegean	East Med	Black
<i>Carte Pisane</i>	θ_{LSE} [°]	9.85°	-	9.0°	8.5°	9.4°	1.1°	3.4°	9.4°	-
<i>Cortona chart</i>	θ_{LSE} [°]	9.73°	-	-	3.2° (7.2°)*	6.6° (10.6°)*	5.5° (9.5°)*	3.3°	9.5°	12.1°
Vesconte composite	θ_{LSE} [°]	10.84°	3.6°	7.9°	9.6°	9.7°	9.3°	9.5°	10.3°	10.3°
magnetic declination for year 1250 according to <i>CALS3k.4</i>	δ_{1250} [°]	-	6.6°	9.3°	9.2°	7.1°	9.2°	6.6°	3.5°	4.1°
<i>Carte Pisane</i>	$\Delta\theta_{LSE}$ [°]	-	-	0.3°	0.6°	2.3°	8.1°	3.2°	5.9°	-
<i>Cortona chart</i>	$\Delta\theta_{LSE}$ [°]	-	-	-	5.9° (1.9°)*	0.5° (3.5°)*	3.7° (0.2°)*	3.3°	5.9°	8.0°
Vesconte composite	$\Delta\theta_{LSE}$ [°]	-	3.0°	1.4°	0.4°	2.6°	0.1°	2.9°	6.8°	6.2°

* Values which would be true if the western part on *Cortona chart* were not relatively tilted 4° clockwise.

¹¹ The earliest known explicit record of the magnetic declination (variation) is from Christopher Columbus's diary. However, according to the pre-Columbian existence of devices in which the sundial and magnetic compass were pieced-together (so called *travellers' companions*, the oldest preserved of which was made in Nuremberg in 1451), and some pre-Columbian testimonies of Portuguese sailors written during their circumnavigations of Africa, it could have been known among the western Europeans for decades before (Taylor 1957: 172-173).

5. A POSSIBLE COMMON ORIGIN

Although the research sample is limited to only a few examples of early-made portolan charts known to exist, the cartometric analyses to which the selected charts were subjected yielded outcomes that strongly suggest that all of them probably originated from the same source. The first outcome which supports the ‘common origin hypothesis’ is the fact that a considerable portion of the Mediterranean Sea’s coastline-contours is nearly identical in appearance on all three charts (Figure 6). The second supportive outcome is the discovery of chart-subsections whose spatial distribution is mainly similar among charts, and whose geometry was not significantly altered (Figure 10).

Chart-subsections are, on average, twice as accurate in comparison to their assembly when treated as a whole, which is paradoxical if portolan charts are considered to be genuine late medieval cartographic products based on contemporary shipborne bearing- and distance-data. If that were the case, it would mean that the sailors of the late Middle Ages – who hypothetically performed those measurements (of which there is no positive historical evidence) – were, in fact, twice as more accurate than the cartographers to whom those data-logs were given, because they failed to assemble them accurately enough. In other words, if the contemporary sailors were so skilled, they would have noticed early enough that bearings on the eastern half of the charts’ extent do not fit well with the compass-north in reality (Table 4), and that the distances measured across different areas on charts do not match scale-wise (Table 3). Also, certain parts of the coastline – like the Gulf of Taranto and Gulf of Corinth in the north, the Gulf of Gabes and Gulf of Sirte in the south, and the Gulf of Iskenderun in the east, for example – were well known to the prominent naval forces of late Middle Ages, and there should be no logical reason why they were drawn so inaccurately on all charts.

Figure 10. The overlay of cartometrically determined coastal subsections on all charts, which does not fully correspond to *International Hydrographic Organisation division of oceans and seas (IHO 1953)*. Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus et al., 2017).

The lack of cartographers' skill to create a mosaic whose accuracy is of the same level as the accuracy of its pieces, is easier to explain if it is assumed that there was a hypothetical cartographic source material that was made before the Middle Ages, and which came into the possession of late medieval Italians (perhaps Genoese), who tried to 'revive' it, and whose attempts to do so were not so skilful. It could have happened, for example, that in the early stages of map-making, the author of *Carte Pisane* unintentionally plotted the Mediterranean Sea coastlines in a map scale that was too large in comparison to the size of the parchment he used, which made him unable to fit the complete rendering of the Black Sea into it at the end (because its eastern half protrudes outside the 'map canvas'; see Figure 1). The same early unwise decision might have been the reason why its Atlantic coasts were rendered so inaccurately – perhaps the author decided that there would be no sense to draw just the Bay of Biscay in its upper-left corner and opted for a skewed and sketchy display of the entire area (Figure 1, Figure 9). Another example is the 4° clockwise tilt of the western wind rose and the coastlines it encircles on the *Cortona chart*, which could be an indicator that the chart was created by a cartographer whose (copying) skills were not so advanced. Vesconte's chart, on the other hand, appears to be remarkably more sophisticated to the naked eye, but it was clearly demonstrated that it contains a large portion of elements that were geometry-wise copied from the material that was already in existence at the time (Figure 5). Truth be told; on his charts, the West Mediterranean is drawn more accurately than on *Carte Pisane*, the Sea of Azov looks more realistic than on *Cortona chart*, and the North Atlantic coast in his 1313 atlas is rendered at the same level of accuracy as the East Mediterranean on his 1311 chart. However, the East Mediterranean on his chart is drawn less accurately in comparison to the *Cortona chart*, and the Central Mediterranean as well as the Adriatic Sea, are drawn less accurately in comparison to both 'less-sophisticated' charts (Table 2).

This is not the first research whose results suggest that there is a high probability that portolan charts are copies of older source-material. Wagner assumed it already in the late nineteenth century, as well as Georges Grosjean and Helmut Minow did more recently (Grosjean 1977; Minow 1998), but the most solid arguments were provided by Nicolai, who performed a sophisticated and detailed geodetic approach to the matter. Nicolai, as well as Tome Marelić (Marelić 2023a), also demonstrated that it is highly unlikely that portolan charts were made upon the measurements obtained during dead-reckoning navigation due to the inefficiency of the supposed plane-charting technique (an idea pursued by the medievalist school of thought), the inevitable accumulation of errors, and the impossibility to sight distant coastal features by using magnetic compass because of the Earth's surface curvature, etc. But still, the most difficult chart-metric to be explained from the pre-medieval origin viewpoint is the western tilt of charts and their sub-parts, which somewhat corresponds to the late medieval eastern magnetic declination values for the Western Mediterranean. In the early eighties, James E. Kelley Jr. assumed that it could be the result of a trilateration network used to survey the area (Kelley 1995: 5-6), which motivated Loomer to use it as one of his planes of reference, but the results were poorer than those obtained in comparison with the Mercator projection on a sub-basin level (Loomer 1987: 144-146).

It is well known that the cartographers of classical antiquity used spherical coordinates to define locations on Earth's surface and developed at least several types of map projections. Marinus of Tyre, for example, was the assumed creator of equidistant cylindrical projection, while Claudius Ptolemy, presumably, invented the equidistant conic projection (so-called *Ptolemy's first projection*)¹² and pseudoconic projection (so-called *Ptolemy's second projection*) (Keuning 1955: 9-10, 13-16; Snyder 1993: 5-8, 10-14). Ptolemy himself stated that the source of the large portion of spatial data in his *Geographike Hyphegesis* (commonly known as *Geography*) was Marinus of Tyre, whose writings and maps are now lost. Although he used Marinus's cylindrical projection for larger-scale maps of smaller areas, Ptolemy criticised its usage for the depiction of the whole *oikumene* on a smaller-scale map because such a map does not show the convergence of meridians, and therefore does not reflect the sphericity of the Earth (Berggren, Jones 2000: 23-41). Ptolemy's spatial data is extremely inaccurate longitude-wise (Marx 2012: 100-102), as well as in comparison to early modern nautical charts with graticules (Marelić 2023b: 28-34), but his *Geography* is the only such work

¹² Normal equidistant conic projection with standard parallel $\phi_0=36^\circ\text{N}$.

from the classical antiquity we know of. Also, the oldest preserved artefacts known to exist are not the original script, but its medieval copies the earliest of which was probably written in thirteenth-century Byzantium (Gautier Dalché 2007: 285–287). Therefore, it is difficult to determine with certainty which parts of its content are true to the original and which are the data-corruptions made in medieval times, and – what is also important – were there, perhaps, any other classical works that are now lost or not yet discovered, and whose data-accuracy was beyond that of *Geography*.

In theory, the typical portolan chart spatial layout could also be generated if the hypothetical earlier-made cartographic source material that came into the possession of late medieval Genoese was, perhaps, an atlas which was segmented into maps with partial depictions of coastlines – each made in cylindrical (equidistant or Mercator-like) projection, and, perhaps, in a different map scale – and which may also have contained an additional general (orientational) map in smaller scale made in a conic projection on which the convergence of meridians is displayed. For example; when the usual territorial coverage of portolan charts is shown on a modern map in *Ptolemy's first projection* set in such a way that the approximate western end of the Mediterranean Sea ($\lambda=6^\circ\text{W}$ near Gibraltar) is selected as its central meridian which is plotted vertically, the meridians of its western section are plotted with tilts which approximately correspond to the values of the *LSE*-induced tilts of the portolan chart subsections on that area (Figure 11, Table 4). Since the late medieval cartographers were unfamiliar with the mechanics of map projections, it could be possible that during their efforts to fit the hypothetical (cylindrical) larger-scale-pieces together by using a hypothetical (conic) smaller-scale-map as a reference model, they could have rotated them slightly in succession from the west towards the east to come to the visually similar end result. It is also possible that in doing so, they replaced the graticules with networks of rhumb lines and added scale-bars to make the charts more suitable for dead reckoning navigation. No matter how far-fetched this hypothesis may seem, it could be partially supported by two separate historical records that, perhaps, refer to the same historical figure. The first one is the so-called *Rex Tholomeus* portolan chart, probably of Genoese origin, and dated to the mid-fourteenth century (c. 1360). The chart contains an illustration of a crowned male human figure (positioned near the city of Alexandria) holding compasses (dividers) in his hand, and with the *Rex Tholomeus* inscription written above his head.¹³ The second one and more explicit is the paragraph from *De Navigatione*, a treatise written in 1464 by Benedetto Cotrugli of Ragusan origin, in which he writes that sailors should be grateful to Ptolemy because the nautical charts that were in use at the time were created by using his maps as templates (Kotruljević 1464 (2005): 216-217).¹⁴

¹³ *Rex Tholomeus* chart and the basic information about it can be accessed at Barry Lawrence Ruderman webpage: <https://www.raremaps.com/gallery/detail/91710/the-rex-tholomeus-portolan-chart-anonymous>

¹⁴ The transcript of Cotrugli's text: ... *Lo qual Ptholomeo fo nel tempo de divio Antonino et scripse mirabilmente. Fo grande astrologo et geometra, et ordinò et divise le mesure et le proportioni dello mare, cielo et terra, et misurò tucto per lo compasso cielesto et describe lo mappamundo donne nui havimo la cartha dello navigare, la qual c'insegna lo andar per mare et non ci lassa errare ... nulla de mino semo multi obligati ad Ptholomeo perché allo giorno de ogi non erramo. Ançi, quello facievano in prima a casu et zero arbitrio, hora havimo reducto per venti et mesure.*

Figure 11. Tilts of subsections of Pietro Vesconte's composite chart obtained in comparison to a modern map in Mercator projection (see Table 4), and the graticule of a modern map that closely approximates *Ptolemy's first projection* if $\lambda=6^{\circ}\text{W}$ (near Gibraltar) is set as its central meridian. Basemap shapefile source: marineregions.org (Claus et al., 2017).

6. CONCLUSIONS

The cartometric analysis of *Carte Pisane*, *Cortona chart*, and two early Pietro Vesconte's charts showed that the majority of their territorial coverage was drawn very similarly to each other, and that significantly large portions of coastlines are drawn nearly identically. Also, the analysis based on the magnitudes and orientations of their displacement vectors revealed that the charts are, most likely, composites made of (coastal) subsections whose borders across the Mediterranean Sea do not match with its traditional subdivision. The accuracy of subsections proved to be, on average, twice as accurate in comparison to the accuracy of charts when they are treated as a whole, which suggests that the cartographers of the late Middle Ages had difficulties joining the chart-pieces together tilt-wise and scale-wise, and, therefore, that it is highly unlikely that the spatial data upon which those pieces were initially created were obtained by the contemporary sailors during their dead reckoning navigations. The fundamental conclusion is that there is a higher probability that the coastline renderings on the earliest known portolan charts are actually more or less skilfully made copies of the (same) source material used as a graphic template. The hypothetical source might have been an atlas whose origins, perhaps, date back to before the Middle Ages, composed of larger-scale maps whose extents were similar to the extents of detected subsections made in a cylindrical (equidistant or Mercator-like) projection and in different map scale. If such an atlas had contained an orientational smaller-scale map made in a conic projection as well, it could, hypothetically, explain the typical regional layout found on portolan charts. Simply put; if the late medieval cartographers, who were not aware of the map projection mechanics, tried to graphically emulate the appearance of the entire area on the map showing the convergence of the meridians, it is possible that when copying parts in the direction from west to east, they rotated each successive copied piece slightly more counterclockwise to obtain a visually similar end result.

STATEMENTS AND DECLARATIONS

COMPETING INTERESTS:

The authors report there is no competing interests to declare.

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